

TEACHING IS THE PROFESSION THAT CREATES ALL OTHER PROFESSIONS

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Annotation. *Teaching is an art. When I first arrived at the school as a teacher, I seriously considered it. This is the art of understanding and listening to children. This is the art of self-discipline. And the most important, that this is the art of loving. You can love someone whom you have already given a piece of your soul.*

Keywords: *giving, loving, profession.*

I have always had a special attitude to the profession of a teacher. I was lucky enough to study from wonderful teachers. Thanks to them, I got more than just knowledge in subjects. They taught me to be fair, to look at the world with smile, to pass everything through my heart and be guided by my conscience. I was always curious that why people became teachers.

So why did I decide to become a teacher? To me, the answer is self-evident. This is one of the most important professions. Teachers are the ones who bring out the best in children. The gardener grows lovely roses and cares for them for a long time. Planting a seed, fertilizing, watering, and hoeing, on the other hand, requires a significant amount of effort. Teachers are like gardeners, and our students are flowers. And, in order for the roses to grow beautifully, each plant requires special care. Some flowers prefer moisture, while others prefer heat. As a result, each child requires a tailored approach. In my work, I make an effort to follow this principle. The teacher's mission, in my opinion, is very important. A teacher's job is to raise a

healthy generation by educating a student who is a patriot of his country, a person with moral values, and a person who understands what does honor, dignity, and conscience mean. It's impossible to raise a student like this without setting a good example for them. We should aspire to be like the teacher, and we should be proud of him or her.

Unfortunately, as in any other job, difficulties may arise in the school life of a teacher. But this has never stopped me, because overcoming problems, we only become stronger and more experienced. It is very important for a teacher to plan his career correctly, find an approach to each student, interest in his subject, infect children with his optimism and desire to learn new things. Of course, a teacher must believe in success. My passion for children influenced my decision to pursue a career in this field. When you work with children, you unintentionally become a big kid yourself, believing in miracles and celebrating small victories.

A teacher is not just a profession, it is both a vocation and a titanic work. This is a difficult, responsible job, but very interesting.

I work as a teacher in Kazakhstan. Education is free for children in my country. My country gives me a lot of opportunities to teach them, too. As we live in independent country it is easier to live. For 30 years of Kazakhstan's Independence, the field of education has been continuously developing and improving. Thanks to the policy implemented by the Head of State Nursultan Nazarbayev, much attention is paid to education and science. However, thanks to the hard work of professionals in their field, who, despite everything, continued to devote themselves to their favorite profession, they were able to bring domestic pedagogy to a new level. In modern conditions, obtaining a high-quality education is the dictate of the time. Therefore, the role of the teacher in the educational process is the main one. Each of our achievement is our country's achievement. Year by year, the title of "teacher" is becoming gorgeous. Teachers' salaries have been increased in last two years. Now teachers don't go for cleaning on Saturdays. They are devoting their time only for educating Kazakhstan's children. The future

of Kazakhstan is perspective and bright. That's why I try to work harder than before. Because teachers play main role in Kazakhstan's society.

Education today is at a turning point in its development and the choice of strategic paths and directions of this development largely determines the prospects not only of domestic education, but also of our country as a whole. At different stages of its development, the society imposed new standards and requirements on the workforce. This led to the development of the education system. This is manifested in the fact that, firstly, the pragmatization of education focused on the increasing needs of a changing knowledge society has emerged, when the multidimensional value of education itself has significantly increased. Following the rapidly developing needs of society has turned traditionally conservative education into a sphere of continuous renewal, the source of which, as a rule, is the state.

The modern labor market conducts rigorous selection, correcting formally free professional choice under the influence of competition and economic demand. The employer evaluates not only the level of qualifications obtained, but also the ability to use the accumulated experience to acquire new competencies in self-development mode. In these conditions, the role of a competence-based approach to training specialists is significantly increasing. According to K. F. Wolf, "innovation is ... the transformation of the old into the new." A person who has the ability for continuous intellectual cognition has not only the ability to know the world around him, but also to constantly expand his field of knowledge. Innovations in education cannot change the processes of higher nervous activity, they only give a person the opportunity to generate new knowledge. A teacher in an innovative education system does not act as a transmitter of knowledge or even as a tutor accompanying a student, but rather as a designer. It depends on his ability to see.

Consequently, the impact of innovations on the effectiveness of the educational process is great. Special attention should be paid to the introduction of information technology as a way to create a unified system combining traditional

and innovative education, modern education aims to develop the ability to learn, the ability to self-development and self-improvement. In general, new technologies in education are necessary and should be combined with traditions to educate a competitive personality. Thus, the use of innovative technologies in education can be useful for both teachers and methodologists of various levels.

For example, the introduction of computer-based learning does not at all imply abandoning traditions and following exclusively the requirements of progress. After all, the Internet, for example, significantly expands the possibilities for exploring those resources that were previously unavailable. Cloud technologies not only allow you to store the necessary files, but also significantly enrich the potential for transferring advanced teaching experience. The exchange of experience takes place not only within the limits limited geographically, but also throughout. Thus, methodological support for improving the level of professional competence of teachers will contribute to changing attitudes towards achieving the quality of education. The introduction of innovative methods, solutions and tools into the domestic education system will allow to activate the activity of a teacher in a new format. Almost a century ago, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor Mark Matusovich Potashnik He said: "It is well known that you can not move forward with your head turned back, and therefore it is unacceptable in the shko.

Literature:

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